

Political interference and its impact on the quality of higher education in Nepalese universities: Stakeholders' perceptions

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Abstract

In this work, the influence of political interferences and student movements on the quality of higher education in Nepalese universities have been investigated on the basis of the perceptions of the university faculty members and students. We have also attempted to reveal the views of faculty members and students regarding government funding, the research environment, the study atmosphere, affordability of education, curriculum updates, and faculty qualifications in Nepalese universities. The finding indicates that there is adverse effect of political interferences on the quality of higher education. The government funding to higher education was thought to be insufficient. There is mixed perceptions of the concerns regarding other issues.

Keywords: Nepal higher education; political interference; government funding; faculty qualification; research environment

INTRODUCTION

Higher education makes a significant contribution to the process of development (Boni & Walker, 2016; McCowan, 2019; Owens, 2017). It has significant potential for the socioeconomic and cultural advancement of the nation while offering individuals the opportunity to flourish in the modern global economy. The role of higher education to sustainable economic and social progress are growing year by year (Cloete et al., 2017). Therefore, the connection between higher education and the development of economies, societies, and cultures has been a central subject of studies concerning the accumulation of human capital (Lucas, 1988; Mankiw et al., 1992).

The historical background of education of Nepal often traced back to 18th century when the Gurkha dynasty was at its peak (Pant, 1985). However, the modern English education system was supposed to be started during Rana regime (1846-1951) who ruled Nepal for about a century until the early 1950s. Throughout the Rana era the access of education was limited to only privileged class. The Rana regime always had fear among the educated public. This can be observed by a feeling shared by the then Prime Minister Chandra Shamsher Rana. Chandra Shamsher Rana, who, in 1918, established Tri-Chandra College expressed his belief that its establishment marked the eventual downfall of Rana rule (Savada, 1991).

The first higher education institution founded in Nepal was Tribhuvan Chandra Intermediate College, later known as Tri-Chandra College (The UGC, Nepal). After the establishment of Tri-Chandra College, some more colleges were established over time (Shakya, 1984; Sharma, 2001). Tribhuvan University was opened in 1959 as the first university in the country (UGC, Nepal). After a long period of rule by the Rana regime, the next decade (1950-1960) was divided into two parts: the first eight years as an interim period covering the era of King Tribhuvan and the early years of King Manendra, and the next two years as the beginning of parliamentary democracy and the dismissal of parliament by King Mahendra in December 1960 (Baral, 1971). In December 1960, the King formally disbanded the party system after almost a decade of struggle and tension between the Nepali Congress party and the monarchy over the locus of legitimate power. He declared the "experiment with multi-party democracy" a failure and disbanded the party

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system. As a replacement, the panchayat system was developed (Caddell 2007). The Panchayat system brought Nepal back into direct kingship around 30 years. Nationalization of education therefore happened with increased vigor following the fall of the multiparty democracy and its replacement by a party-less Panchayat style of administration. This is due to the Panchayat system's use of education—particularly the curriculum—to replace the preexisting multiethnic and multilingual society with a single Nepali ethnic group. There were more works on the improvement of education in the primary schools (Onta, 1996).

In spite of their efforts to expand education, senior members of the Panchayat System seemed to realize the dangers of continuing the undemocratic Panchayat system. The anti-Panchayat movement was successful since educated young people did not support the Pan-chayat system (Hoftun et al., 1999). King Birendra eventually announced that he would restore multiparty democracy, and the party ban was lifted on 8 April 1990, ending the pan-chayat system. In 1991, Kathmandu University was opened as the first private university of the country. During the late 1980s and 1990s, additional universities like Mahendra Sanskrit University, Purbanchal University, Siddhartha University, and Pokhara University were established (UGC, Nepal, 2015; Worldmark Encyclopedia of Nations, 2007). Currently, several new universities are running to provide higher education in Nepal, and some more are in the process of being established.

Although numerous universities have been founded in Nepal to provide higher education to its public, the quality of higher education has not advanced as expected since the establishment of Tribhuvan University (UGC, 2015). The significance of higher education as a driver of Nepal's overall development has been firmly established (ADB, 2015; Upadhyay, 2018; Yogendra, 2021). Nevertheless, the attainment of a "healthy and sustainable" development of higher education remains a major challenge in the country (Baral, 2016). Elevating Nepali higher education to meet global standards necessitates substantial policy innovations (Koirala, 2014). The issues and hurdles pertaining to higher education in Nepal have a range of dimensions, including equitable access and its expansion, the relevance and enhancement of quality, institutional governance, innovative capacity, the implementation of reforms to ensure educational quality and organizational effectiveness (ADB, 2015).

In comparison to neighboring nations, Nepalese universities have not shown the expected improvement ("World University Ranking," 2023). After the 1990s, appointments to key positions in universities, such as Vice Chancellors, Rectors, Deans, Campus Chiefs, and so on, have been influenced by political orientation rather than being based on academic performance. Some people argue that appointments of administrative staff and faculty members have also been influenced by political considerations. Such non-academic activities raise questions about the qualifications of faculty members and the ability of universities to deliver high-quality education. The quality of education and academic life in

Nepalese universities are also affected by student movements, protests, and strikes.

In this study, we attempt to investigate the perceptions of faculty members and students regarding impact of political interference on various aspects of quality of education, including government funding, research environment, and study atmosphere, affordability of education, curriculum updates, and faculty qualifications. The central issue to be addressed is why, despite the establishment of numerous universities and colleges the quality of higher education has not progressed as expected in comparison to neighboring nations.

METHOD

To conduct the study, we employed a mixed-methods research approach; both quantitative and qualitative data collection methodologies (Almalki, 2017). We attempted to include university faculty members and student covering various age groups ranging from 20-29, 30-39, 40-49, and 50 and above and different geographic regions representing different provinces. A similar attempt has been made to cover a wide range of educational qualifications, spanning from bachelor's level to doctoral degrees.

We used both purposive and snowball sampling methods. For purposive sampling, participants were choosing in such a way that they were important to meet our study goals. For purposive sampling, we first sent questionnaires to university faculty members who were working in different decisive positions. The students were also chosen for purposive sampling who were representative of student unions. This method helped us make sure that people from a wide range of backgrounds and skills were represented. Then we used a snowball sampling method to get more people to join. People who had already filled out the poll were asked to get others to do so as well. This would increase the number of different points of view.

A total of 156 participants took part in our survey. Eighteen objective questions were asked to the participants. The questions were designed in such a way that the respondents could evaluate the political interference on appointments of key positions like Vice Chancellor, Rector, Deans, Campus Chiefs etc. as well as faculty members and administrative staffs in different universities and its impact on the quality of higher education. The participants were also asked to share their views regarding the presence of student movements, protests and strikes in universities. The questionnaires were also designed to extract the opinions of respondents about the government funding and resource affordability in Nepalese universities. Apart from this, the respondents could examine the research and study environments, qualification of faculty members and timely curriculum updates using the questionnaires given to them. Participants were also provided with open questions so that they could give additional comments and express their thoughts and recommendations.

To understand the relationship among various factors, we conducted cross-tabulation analysis on the data obtained from the survey. Then a statistical analysis was done to identify the general trends and patterns. We also did thematic analysis using

the comments and suggestions of participants to identify the valuable insights. This mixed-methods approach allowed us to gain a general view on the impact of political and government influences on higher education in Nepal.

RESULTS

The participants' summary regarding their age, gender, occupation, qualifications, and demographic information is presented in Table 1. It is found that approximately 88.4 % of the respondents had a common view that there is political influence on the appointment of key positions of universities. These key positions included Vice-Chancellor, Rector, Dean, Campus Chief etc. Approximately 81% of participants believed that the political influence occurs to the selection of administrative staff and faculty members. Most notably, a substantial 88.4% of the respondents felt that the political interferences had an adverse effect on the quality of education within Nepalese universities. Most of the respondents of different age groups and educational degrees agree that political interference in university appointments has a negative impact on the quality of education. Table 2 shows the cross-tabulation between "Witnessed/Experienced Political Interference" and "Quality of Education Impact".

We performed a chi-square test to assess the impact of political interference on the quality of higher education in Nepalese universities. The test was done to prove or disprove the following hypotheses:

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no observable association between instances of Witnessed/Experienced Political Interference and the Impact on the Quality of Education.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): A correlation exists between instances of Witnessed/Experienced Political Interference and the Impact on the Quality of Education.

In order to find the total chi square value, we ensured the following procedures. The expected frequency for each was computed using the formula

$$\text{Expected Frequency} = (\text{Row Total} \times \text{Column Total}) / \text{Grand Total}$$

The chi square statistic for each variable was calculated with the relation

$$\text{Chi-square value} = \sum (\text{observed frequency} - \text{expected frequency})^2 / \text{expected frequency}$$

The degree of freedom was determined as

$$\text{Degrees of freedom} = [(\text{Number of Rows} - 1) \times (\text{Number of Columns} - 1)]$$

The total chi square value was found as 31.608. We looked at a chi-square distribution table to determine the critical value for four degrees of freedom based on our selected significance level, which is usually set at 5%, in order to comprehend the significance of our findings. The critical value in this instance is approximately 9.49.

Regarding the student movements, protests and strikes within Nepali universities, 75% of the respondents believed that these

movements have negative impact on the quality of education (Table 3). 7.7 % percent of respondents said these movements had no significant effect on the quality of education, while 17.3% of respondents thought they had a positive impact. The respondents who believed that student movements, protests and strikes had positive impact on higher education were mostly students. Most of the faculty members, however, believed that these movements had a harmful effect on higher education.

We calculated a chi-square value to understand the relation between "Occupation" and "Influence of Student Movements on Education Quality". We followed the similar procedure to determine the chi-square value in this case. The total chi-square value obtained was 50.69. To evaluate the significance of our findings, we observed a chi-square distribution table to identify the critical value for 2 degrees of freedom, based on our chosen significance level, typically set at 5%. In this case, the critical value was approximately 5.99.

Shifting our focus to faculty qualifications, the survey detected a varied view. 61% of participants thought that faculty members possessed qualifications to some extent. However, a more optimistic perspective was held by 31% of the respondents, who were confident about the qualifications of faculty members. 8% of the respondents expressed concerns about faculty qualifications.

In our study, most of the respondents (85%) felt that government funding for higher education was insufficient. Few respondents (13%) felt that government funding was sufficient. The respondents had differing opinions regarding the policies of government on higher education. Approximately 26% of the respondents had a negative opinion regarding these policies where as 31% thought they were good. A small numbers of participants (6%) were not sure in this matter, and 37% thought they had no significant effect.

It was found that 8% of the respondents thought the study environment at Nepalese universities was poor, 35% thought it was fair, 48% thought it was good and 8% thought it was very good. The respondents also gave their opinions regarding the educational cost in the higher education. 42% of the respondents thought educational cost were reasonable, and 48% thought they were not. Responses of the participants for the assessment of the research environment in Nepalese universities were mixed. Of the respondents, 32% thought it was poor, 33% thought it was fair, 25% thought it was good, and 10% thought it was very good.

In terms of curriculum updates, 42% reported that they occurred occasionally, while 38% believed they happened rarely. A smaller 10% indicated that curriculum updates were frequent. The opinions of the respondents on library resources revealed that 56% considered them adequate to some extent, while 40% believed they were not adequately equipped to support academic and research activities.

Table 1: Summary of Characteristics of the Participants

Age		Number participants on the basis of							
		Gender		Education		Occupation		Location	
20-29	23	Male	124	Bachelors	12	Faculty	116	Koshi	46
30-39	21	Female	32	Masters	73	Student	40	Madhesh	13
40-49	47			M. Phil.	17			Bagmati	44
50 & above	65			Ph. D.	46			Gandaki	23
								Lumbini	15
								Karnali	8
								Sudurpaschim	7

Table 2: Witnessed/Experienced Political Interference and Quality of Education Impact

Witnessed/Experienced Political Interference	Quality of Education Impact					Total
	Significant	Moderate	Minor	No Impact	No Idea	
Yes	126	9	0	0	3	138
No	12	2	1	1	2	18
Total	138	11	1	1	5	156

Table 3: Respondents' Perspectives regarding the Impact of Student Movements on the Quality of Higher Education

Occupation	Influence of Student Movements on Education Quality			Total
	Yes, positively	No, negatively	No influence	
Faculty member	5	106	5	116
Student	22	11	7	40
Total	27	117	12	156

Table 4: Respondents' Perceptions Concerning the Affordability of Educational Costs in Universities

Occupation	Education cost in universities			Total
	Affordable	Not affordable	No idea	
Faculty member	55	56	5	116
Student	10	19	11	40
Total	65	75	16	156

DISCUSSION

The findings of this investigation underline a remarkable issue: the involvement of politics in the selection of university leadership or key positions, and other higher education appointments, negatively affects the quality of education. The cross-tabulation, as presented in Table 2, provides clear evidence that a significant proportion of the study participants hold the view that political interference has adverse consequences on the quality of education. The consensus among participants regarding the adverse influence of political interfering points to an instant requirement for addressing this

matter to uphold high academic standards. The result of chi-square test also clearly indicates that there is a significant effect of political interference on the quality of higher education.

Table 2 provides evident insights into the presence of varying perspectives between faculty members and students regarding the impact of student movements on the quality of education. These divergent viewpoints concerning student movements imply the necessity for enhanced communication and collaboration between students and educational institutions. The result of chi-square test between "Occupation" and "Influence of Student Movements on Education Quality" suggests that faculty members and students have differing perspectives on how student movements affect education quality. Further analysis may be needed to understand the nature of this association and the reasons behind these differing perceptions. Simultaneously, the differences in perceptions regarding faculty qualifications indicate the importance of implementing rigorous faculty recruitment and professional development procedures.

The fact that most people agree that government funding is insufficient shows the urgent need to secure more financial resources. Moreover, the majority rating the research environment as poor or fair indicates a need for investment in research facilities. Since respondents had mixed feelings about the education environment, it is clear that improvements in Nepali universities are necessary. The opinions from 48% of respondents who indicated that the higher education in Nepali universities is not affordable highlights the importance of addressing tuition fees and making resources more accessible. Table 4 provides a summary of the respondents' perceptions concerning the affordability of educational costs in universities. Mixed perceptions regarding faculty qualifications indicate the need for rigorous faculty development and selection standards.

Moreover, the rarity of curriculum updates, as reported by 38% of respondents, indicates the need to revise curricula to align with industry demands. Finally, the reported inadequacy of library resources by 40% of respondents implies the necessity of enhancing academic and research support.

We compare case studies of political interference and how it affects the standard of higher education in Nepal and a few Indian states. India is among the nations with robust economies. Comparatively speaking to other states, West Bengal (WB) and Bihar states in India have a lot more political interference in higher education. This is the reason why there are no well-paying employment accessible in the Indian states of West Bengal and Bihar and why the quality of education in those regions is currently deteriorating. In fact, political interference in university matters has an impact on India's higher education system's quality as well (Kirya, 2019).

In the case of European Union, the appointment of the Rector and VC has freedom in the universities within the EU nations. Additionally, in many countries academic posts are filled by a competitive in EU nations (Karran, 2007). Regarding academic freedom, rector appointment systems in US and Turkish universities select their rector from outside the university and through election by the administrative board (Tuncer, 2022). A rector may be chosen by the board or elected by the university in the United States (Gray et al., 2005; Taylor & de Lourdes, 2008).

Within a university's organizational structure, the function of presidents (chancellors/rectors) and the selection processes for them are vital. Since representativeness, accountability, transparency, and participation are key indicators of an institution's democratic culture, selection procedures should be given more consideration as they should form the cornerstone of all universities of United States and the United Kingdom (Teket et al., 2013)

Researchers have examined the university teacher recruitment and selection processes in the United States and Germany. Based on Chinese national circumstances and educational practices, they have proposed a university teacher access system. This means that the development of high-level universities, the cultivation of elite talent, and the production of first-rate scientific research can only occur through the establishment of an efficient incentive and restraint system that creates internal driving forces for teaching staff and level promotion (Zhang et al., 2015).

Tribhuvan University used application forms, selection exams, interviews, appointments, and placements as part of its selection procedure for this reason. However, there are a few important elements missing from this selection procedure, which include the background check, screening, references, and medical exams Mathis et al. (2012) note. Due to this flaw in the selection process, TU chooses to fill open positions with substandard individuals. TU therefore suffers greatly from low work performance, productivity, and effectiveness inside the

company, which has a general negative impact on its global position (Shrestha, 2020).

Multiple parties came together to establish Nepal's current administration. Rather of dividing academic institutions based on merit, the Nepali government did so based on political considerations. The majority of political parties nowadays have taken a lesson from the educated youth who overthrew the Panchayat system. In light of this, the current administration does not want to retain or hire educated youth, which is why there is an excessive amount of youth migration in Nepal, making it easier to reign over children and the elderly. The remaining educated individuals in Nepal who are active in politics have the opportunity to choose university leadership and staff, leadership roles, and other appointments related to higher education. Political participation personnel constantly harasses educated youth who have received their education abroad and wish to return home, without considering how to improve the quality of education.

Even though Tribhuvan University and other universities have included provisions for a students' union in their legislation, student politics in Nepal have unintentionally hindered academic pursuits. It is somewhat disheartening that there are more non-academic activities taking place on campus than teaching-learning activities.

In Nepal, poor salaries, political unpredictability, and a lack of work prospects were the primary causes of brain drain. The additional causes of the brain drain were a bad working environment, inadequate education, corruption, nepotism, and favoritism in the hiring process (Mainali, 2019).

Limitations

The study might have a number of limitations. The sample selection might be one of the drawbacks. It is possible that the sample we chose is not entirely representative of the whole population. For instance, the study contains comments from faculty members and students at universities. It might not, however, address the viewpoints of other significant stakeholders, like alumni or public. This sampling bias may restrict how broadly the results can be applied. Bias in self-reporting could be another drawback. Surveys are used in this study to gather data. It is possible that the respondents do not always give completely unbiased information. The results could be impacted if respondents give false information about their experiences or beliefs.

Recommendation

To address the identified challenges, a set of recommendations is proposed. Firstly, it is crucial to establish transparent, merit-based processes for all university appointments, especially key positions. Secondly, initiating constructive dialogues between students and educational authorities is essential to minimize disruptions and foster a collaborative environment. Thirdly, there is a need to prioritize and increase funding to ensure that universities have the necessary resources for delivering quality education. Additionally, investing in faculty development and

implementing rigorous meritocratic standards in the selection process is vital. Furthermore, allocating resources to enhance research infrastructure and regularly updating educational resources within universities is essential for fostering innovation and academic excellence. Lastly, addressing tuition fees and aligning curricula with industry needs will contribute to a more accessible and industry-relevant higher education system.

Conclusion

The study confirms that there is political interference on the major appointments in the universities of Nepal and these interferences have significant impact on the quality of higher education. Student movements, protests and strikes has adverse effect on academic life. It is revealed that government funding is insufficient to upgrade resources. There is also need of improvement on research and study environment in the universities of Nepal.

Ethical approval: The research includes human participants and the data were collected upon receiving informed consent from the participants.

Consent to participate: The participants were informed the process of research report.

Availability of data: Data are available in the article.

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